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Utilization of Innovative Strategies in Teaching Financial Accounting for Improved Performance among Secondary School Students in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the utilization of innovative strategies in teaching financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State. Two purpose of the study, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprises of 345 accounting teachers. The entire population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Innovative Strategies in Teaching Financial Accounting For Improved Performance Questionnaire (ISTFAIPQ)”. The research questions were analyzed with mean and standard deviation while ANOVA was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance. Findings in the revealed that; Flipped classroom strategies and Gamification strategies were utilized in teaching financial accounting. Based on the findings, conclusions and recommendations were made.

Keywords: Accounting, Financial Accounting, Flipped classroom, Gamification.

INTRODUCTION

Accounting is an integral part of the curriculum, providing students with essential knowledge about financial management. Accounting is the process of delivering financial information regarding a business's transactions, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions about the organization's financial activities. According to Oladele (2019), accounting involves maintaining financial records of revenue and expenditure, as well as tracking the flow of funds into and out of an organization. There are two main branches of accounting: financial accounting and management accounting. This study focuses on financial accounting, as it includes key aspects such as manufacturing accounts (manufacturers' final accounts).

Financial accounting, as defined as the process of identifying, measuring, and communicating economic information. In addition, it is used to report an organization's financial data to users for objective assessment and decision-making. Financial accounting specifically deals with the reporting of financial information, making it crucial for understanding the financial health and performance of a business. It compiles and summarizes financial data to prepare reports such as balance sheets and income statements for management, investors, lenders, suppliers, tax authorities, and other stakeholders. This specialized branch of accounting meticulously tracks a company's financial transactions. According to Okiridu, & Bupo, (2018), the primary purpose of financial accounting is to mitigate principal-agent problems by measuring and monitoring agents' performance and subsequently reporting these results to interested

users. The significance of financial accounting spans all sectors of the economy. For employees, it helps assess the potential for job continuity and remuneration levels. The general public can evaluate employment opportunities and socio-economic issues, while the government relies on financial accounting for corporate taxation purposes. Investment analysts use financial data to gauge investment potential based on past and future performance, management strength, and risk-reward ratios. Additionally, financial accounting enables lenders to determine a company's capacity to service debt and repay capital

The general objectives of financial accounting as cited by Anand, McDermott, Mudambi, and Narula, (2021) include: developing a better understanding of business activities and becoming familiar with papers and forms commonly used in business transactions; having an understanding and appreciation of the values and possibilities for record-keeping, personal needs, vocational preparation or preparation for further education; have an understanding of assets, liabilities and proprietorship as well as to enable students interpret business situation correctly and to determine essential financial accounting traits which include accuracy, orderliness, neatness and responsibilities. Olaye, Olatunji, and Ibukun-Falayi, (2020) opined that Financial accounting encompasses various aspects, including knowledge of basic accounting principles, double entry, books of original entry, cash book, trial balance, manufacturing accounts, partnership accounts, company accounts, and more to effectively manage and interpret financial data in their future careers is known as financial accounting skills.

Financial accounting is the process of recording, summarizing, and reporting the myriad of transactions resulting from business operations over a period of time. According to Weygandt, Kimmel and Kieso (2019), financial accounting is concerned with the preparation of financial statements for external users, such as investors, creditors, and tax authorities, which emphasizes the external reporting aspect of financial accounting. Hoggett, Edwards and Medlin (2012) ,define financial accounting as the field of accounting that focuses on providing information to external users through financial statements, underlining the importance of transparency and accountability. Meigs and Meigs (1995), describe financial accounting as the process of identifying, measuring, and communicating economic information to permit informed judgments and decisions by users of the information. This highlights the decision-making utility of financial accounting.

Anthony, Hawkins and Merchant (2011), view financial accounting as a system that provides information about the financial position, performance, and changes in financial position of an entity that is useful to a wide range of users in making economic decisions. This definition emphasizes the broad utility of financial accounting information. Horngren, Harrison and Oliver (2011), define financial accounting as the area of accounting that focuses on reporting an entity's financial status to external parties, highlighting its role in financial disclosure. Williams, Haka, Bettner and Carcello (2015), explain financial accounting as the field of accounting that prepares financial reports for use by people outside the organization, such as shareholders and creditors. This underscores the importance of financial accounting in external communication. Libby, Libby and Short (2019), define financial accounting as the process of preparing financial statements that show an entity's financial performance and position to external users, focusing on the informative role of financial statements.

Kieso, Weygandt and Warfield (2019), describe financial accounting as the preparation of financial reports that cover the financial performance and financial position of a business, intended for external users such as investors and regulatory agencies. This definition highlights the regulatory and investment-related aspects of financial accounting. Stickney and Weil (2016) emphasize that financial accounting involves the process of summarizing, analyzing, and reporting financial transactions to provide useful information to external stakeholders, focusing on the analytical aspect of financial accounting. Brealey, Myers and Marcus (2014), define financial accounting as the process of preparing financial statements that provide information about a firm's operations and financial position to external parties, such as investors and creditors. This emphasizes the operational and financial disclosure functions of financial accounting. Lastly, Atrill and McLaney (2018), describe financial accounting as the practice of preparing financial statements that provide a summary of an organization's financial performance and position to external users, highlighting the summarization aspect.

Financial accounting involves recording, summarizing, and reporting financial transactions to provide useful information to external users. Weygandt, Kimmel and Kieso (2019) and Hoggett, Edwards and Medlin (2012) emphasize the preparation of financial statements for external users, underscoring the importance of transparency and accountability in financial reporting. Meigs and Meigs (1995), highlight the role of financial accounting in facilitating informed decision-making by identifying, measuring, and communicating economic information. Financial accounting is the systematic process of recording, summarizing, and reporting an entity's financial transactions to prepare financial statements that provide useful information about the entity's financial performance and position to external users such as investors, creditors, and regulatory agencies, thereby facilitating informed decision-making and ensuring transparency and accountability in financial reporting.

Flipped learning is an instructional strategy that reverses the traditional learning environment by delivering instructional content outside of the classroom, often online, and using class time for engaging in interactive and application-based activities. Bond (2020), defined flipped learning as a pedagogical approach in which direct instruction moves from the group learning space to the individual learning space, and the resulting group space is transformed into a dynamic, interactive learning environment. This emphasizes the shift of lecture-based instruction to homework and the use of class time for interactive activities. According to Santos and Serpa (2020), flipped learning is a teaching method that inverts the traditional classroom by delivering instructional content online outside of class and moving homework and practice into the classroom, highlighting the inversion of lecture and homework activities to enhance classroom engagement. Furthermore, flipped learning involves students watching pre-recorded lectures at home and engaging in concept mastery exercises in class, thereby focusing on the use of pre-recorded content for home study and active learning during class (Zain & Sailin, 2020).

Flipped learning is a model where students first learn new content outside of class, usually through video lessons, and then use class time for exercises, projects, or discussions that reinforce learning. Ekineh (2022) and Cevikbas and Kaiser (2020), emphasize the initial exposure to new content outside the classroom and in-class reinforcement activities. Furthermore, Sosa Díaz, Guerra Antequera and Cerezo Pizarro (2021) defined flipped learning as a blended learning model that integrates online educational content with traditional classroom methods, shifting instructional time to student-centered learning activities. They describe flipped learning as a blend of online and traditional methods to promote student-centered learning. Cueva and Inga (2022) opined that flipped learning uses online videos to deliver lecture content, allowing classroom time to be used for active learning strategies and personalized instruction, explaining the use of online videos for lectures and active learning in the classroom.

Flipped learning involves delivering content through digital means outside of class, while in-class time is reserved for interactive, student-centered activities. Zawilinski, Shattuck, and Hansen (2020), highlight the digital delivery of content and interactive classroom activities. Flipped learning is a model in which students receive initial instruction via online materials outside of class and engage in collaborative, hands-on learning activities during class. Staker and Horn emphasize online initial instruction and collaborative in-class learning while Mojtahedi, Kamardeen, Rahmat, and Ryan (2020) opined that Flipped learning is a teaching strategy where the first exposure to new material happens before class, freeing up class time for more active, student-centered learning experiences, highlighting pre-class exposure to new material and active in-class learning experiences. Flipped learning is an instructional approach that reverses traditional learning by having students first encounter new material outside of class, typically via video lectures, and then use classroom time for deeper exploration and application, focusing on the reversal of traditional learning and deeper in-class exploration and application (Hava, 2021). Therefore, flipped learning is an instructional approach that shifts direct instruction from the classroom to individual study through online content, such as video lectures, allowing classroom time to be used for interactive, collaborative, and student-centered activities that reinforce and deepen understanding.

Gamification in learning involves applying game-design elements and principles in non-game contexts to enhance user engagement and learning outcomes. Triantafyllou and Georgiadis (2022), describe gamification as the use of game design elements in non-game contexts to improve user experience and engagement, incorporating mechanics such as points, badges, and leaderboards to make learning activities

more engaging. Christopoulos and Mystakidis (2023), similarly define gamification as the process of making activities more game-like by adding elements like challenges, feedback, and rewards to increase motivation and participation. Luo (2022), explains that gamification uses game-based mechanics, aesthetics, and thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solves problems, highlighting its potential to enhance motivation and engagement through game-like experiences. Pfeiffer, Bezzina, König, and Kriglstein (2020) define gamification as applying game principles and mechanics to non-game activities to make them more fun and engaging, transforming mundane tasks into enjoyable activities. Zadeja and Bushati (2022) describe gamification as using game mechanics and dynamics to drive game-like engagement in a non-game context, emphasizing the creation of game-like experiences to increase participation and interest. Parapanos and Michopoulou (2021) view gamification as a process of enhancing a service with affordances for gameful experiences to support the user's overall value creation, focusing on enhancing user experience and satisfaction.

Furthermore, Costello (2020), sees gamification as using game thinking and mechanics to engage audiences and solve problems, emphasizing the motivational and problem-solving aspects. Sanchez, van Oostendorp, Fijnheer and Lavoué (2020), describe gamification as using game design elements in non-game contexts to improve user engagement, satisfaction, and enjoyment, focusing on its positive impact on user experience. Kim (2015), defines gamification as using game mechanics and experience design to digitally engage and motivate people to achieve their goals, highlighting digital tools' role in enhancing engagement. Poonsawad, Srisomphan, and Sanrach (2022), explain gamification as using game elements to create meaningful engagement by connecting the experience to the user's real-world context, emphasizing relevance and meaningfulness in gamified experiences. AlSaad and Durugbo (2021), describe gamification as using game thinking and mechanics to solve problems and engage users, focusing on its potential to improve problem-solving and engagement. From the definitions above, the researcher defines gamification as integrating game-design elements and principles, such as points, badges, leaderboards, and challenges, into non-game contexts to enhance engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes by creating interactive, enjoyable, and meaningful experiences.

Statement of the Problem

The performance of secondary school students in financial accounting in Rivers State has been consistently below expectations, as evidenced by low pass rates and poor comprehension of key accounting concepts. Traditional teaching methods, such as rote memorization and lecture-based instruction, remain predominant in many classrooms. These methods often fail to engage students actively or develop the critical thinking, problem-solving, and practical application skills essential for mastering financial accounting. In an era where technology and innovative pedagogical approaches are transforming education globally, the reliance on outdated instructional strategies in Rivers State is particularly concerning. The limited use of interactive learning activities, modern technology, and real-world applications in teaching financial accounting has resulted in a significant gap between the skills students acquire in school and those required for academic and professional success.

Consequently, the educational resources in Rivers State are often inadequate, exacerbating the challenges faced by both teachers and students. There is an urgent need to explore and implement innovative teaching strategies that can make financial accounting more engaging, accessible, and relevant to students. These strategies include interactive methods such as integrating technology with tools like interactive whiteboards and accounting software; adopting the flipped classroom model; and utilizing project-based learning and gamification techniques.

Research indicates that such innovative approaches can significantly enhance student engagement, understanding, and performance in financial accounting (Akinbobola, 2015; Eze, 2016). However, there is a lack of empirical evidence on their effectiveness within the specific context of secondary schools in Rivers State. This study aims to fill that gap by measuring the extent of utilizing innovative teaching strategies to improve the performance of secondary school students in financial accounting in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to measure the extent to which utilizing innovative teaching strategies can improve the performance of secondary school students in financial accounting in Rivers State. Specifically, the study will be to;

1. To determine the extent to which flipped classroom strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. To determine the extent to which gamification strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent can flipped classroom strategies be applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. To what extent can gamification strategies be applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The study will test the following hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference on the mean rating of financial accounting teachers in the three senatorial districts in Rivers State on the extent to which flipped classroom strategies can be applied for improved performance among secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference on the mean rating of financial accounting teachers in the three senatorial districts in Rivers State on the extent to which gamification strategies can be applied for improved performance among secondary school students.

METHODOLOGY

The study was on the extent of Utilization of Innovative Strategies in Teaching Financial Accounting for Improved Performance among Secondary School Students in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consist of 345 accounting teachers. The entire population was used for the study. Two purposes, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled ““Innovative Strategies In Teaching Financial Accounting For Improved Performance Questionnaire (ISTFAIPQ)” The instrument was structured on a four point rating skills of High Extent (HE) = 4, Moderate Extent (ME) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. The instrument was subjected to face and content by three experts (two in Business Education and one in measurement and education department). Cronbach’s alpha test of reliability was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Twenty (18) copies of the questionnaire were administered to Business Studies teachers at Akwa-Ibom public secondary schools who were not part of the study population, and the computation yielded a coefficient of 0.80 which proves that the instrument is reliable. This shows that the research instrument is reliable. The copies of the research instrument were administered to the respondent used in this study, Mean and Standard Deviation were used in analyzing the research questions while ANOVA was used in testing the hypotheses formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question one: *To what extent can flipped classroom strategies be applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1 mean and standard deviation on the extent to which flipped classroom strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State. N=323

S/	Item Statement	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	I apply real-world scenarios in class to concepts learned from pre-class materials.	2.44	1.12	Moderate Extent
2	I assign articles related to financial accounting for students to complete outside of class.	2.44	1.12	Moderate Extent
3	My students have access to clear and organized pre-class materials.	2.43	1.16	Moderate Extent
4	I utilize educational technology tools like learning management systems, to support pre-class learning.	2.49	1.13	moderate Extent
5	The use of pre-class video lectures helps students' understanding of financial accounting	2.44	1.09	Moderate Extent
6	I regularly monitor and assess students' engagement with pre-class materials	2.52	1.12	High Extent
Grand mean		2.05	1.12	Moderate Extent

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

The results presented in the table below show the mean and standard deviation regarding the extent to which flipped classroom strategies are applied in teaching financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State. The findings indicate that respondents apply real-world scenarios to concepts learned from pre-class materials to a moderate extent (mean = 2.44, SD = 1.12). Teachers assign articles related to financial accounting for students to complete outside of class to a moderate extent (mean = 2.32, SD = 1.11). Students have access to clear and organized pre-class materials to a moderate extent (mean = 2.43, SD = 1.16). Educational technology tools, such as learning management systems, are utilized to support pre-class learning to a moderate extent (mean = 2.49, SD = 1.13). The use of pre-class video lectures enhances students' understanding of financial accounting to a moderate extent (mean = 2.46, SD = 1.09). Teachers also regularly monitor and assess students' engagement with pre-class materials to a moderate extent (mean = 2.52, SD = 1.12). Therefore, the grand mean of 2.44 and standard deviation of 1.12 indicate that, to a moderate extent, flipped classroom strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *To determine the extent to which gamification strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State.*

To answer research question 2, the study examined the responses to items 7-12 of the questionnaire, with the findings clearly and systematically presented in Table 4.2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the extent to which gamification strategies are applied in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State.

N=323				
S/NO	Item Statement	MEAN	S. D	Remark
7	I use game-based learning platforms to reinforce accounting concepts.	2.59	1.16	High Extent
8	I incorporate leaderboards and achievement badges to motivate students.	2.39	1.13	Moderate Extent
9	I apply point systems for class participation and completion of accounting tasks.	2.47	1.15	Moderate Extent
10	I utilize digital badges and certificates to acknowledge student achievements in accounting	2.48	1.14	Moderate Extent
11	It helps me provide instant feedback through game-based activities to aid understanding.	2.46	1.11	Moderate Extent
12	I regularly assess the effectiveness of gamification strategies in enhancing student performance.	2.51	1.16	High Extent
Grand mean		2.48	1.14	Moderate Extent

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

The results displayed in Table 4.1 illustrate the mean and standard deviation concerning the extent to which gamification strategies are utilized in teaching financial accounting to enhance the performance of secondary school students in Rivers State. The data indicates that respondents employ game-based learning platforms to reinforce accounting concepts to a high extent (mean = 2.59, SD = 1.16). Teachers use leaderboards and achievement badges to motivate students to a moderate extent (mean = 2.39, SD = 1.13). Point systems for class participation and task completion in accounting are applied to a moderate extent (mean = 2.47, SD = 1.15). Digital badges and certificates are used to recognize student achievements in accounting to a moderate extent (mean = 2.48, SD = 1.14). Instant feedback through game-based activities is provided to enhance understanding to a moderate extent (mean = 2.46, SD = 1.11). Additionally, the effectiveness of gamification strategies in boosting student performance is regularly evaluated to a high extent (mean = 2.51, SD = 1.16). In summary, the grand mean of 2.48 and standard deviation of 1.14 suggest that gamification strategies are applied to a moderate extent in teaching financial accounting for better student performance in Rivers State secondary schools.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1; There is no significant difference on the mean rating of financial accounting teachers in the three senatorial districts in Rivers State on the extent to which flipped classroom strategies can be applied for improved performance among secondary school students.

To test the hypothesis, the data was analyzed using MS Excel and the result shown in Table 4.9

Table 3: ANOVA results showing the significance of differences in mean responses among financial accounting teachers in the three senatorial districts of Rivers State on the extent to which flipped classroom strategies are applied for improved performance among secondary school students. N=323

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance			
Rivers East	105	258.83	2.47	0.21			
Rivers West	127	311.50	2.45	0.21			
Rivers South	89	223.33	2.51	0.20			
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F- Cal	P-value	F crit	Remark
Between Groups	0.18	2	0.09	0.42	0.66	3.02	retained
Within Groups	66.55	318	0.21				
Total	66.73	320					

The p-value in the table is 0.66, which is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05. Since the p-value (0.66) is greater than 0.05, This means that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean ratings of financial accounting teachers across the three senatorial districts regarding the extent to which flipped classroom strategies can be applied for improved performance among secondary school students. In summary, based on the p-value, the hypothesis can be retained.

Hypothesis 2; There is no significant difference on the mean rating of financial accounting teachers in the three senatorial districts in Rivers State on the extent to which gamification strategies can be applied for improved performance among secondary school students.

Table 4: ANOVA Results Showing the Significance of Differences in the Mean Ratings of Financial Accounting Teachers in the Three Senatorial Districts of Rivers State on the Extent to Which Gamification Strategies Can Be Applied for Improved Performance Among Secondary School Students N=323

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance			
Rivers East	106	267.67	2.53	0.20			
Rivers West	127	318.00	2.50	0.23			
Rivers South	89	215.00	2.42	0.18			
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F-cal	P-value	F crit	Remark
Between Groups	0.64	2.00	0.32	1.54	0.22	3.02	retain
Within Groups	66.58	319.00	0.21				
Total	67.22	321.00					

Source: Field Date, 2024

The ANOVA results reveal that there are no significant differences in how secondary school teachers from Rivers East, Rivers West, and Rivers South apply gamification strategies in teaching financial accounting. The analysis shows a Sum of Squares (SS) of 0.64 for between groups and 66.58 for within groups, with Degrees of Freedom (df) of 2 for between groups and 319 for within groups. The Mean Squares (MS) are 0.32 and 0.21, respectively. The calculated F-value is 1.54, and the P-value is 0.22, which is higher than the significance level of 0.05. The F-critical value at a 0.05 significance level with 2

and 319 df is 3.02. Since the P-value exceeds this threshold, the null hypothesis is retained, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in the application of these learning strategies among the three groups.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section contains the discussion of the results. The discussion was done based on the research questions asked and hypotheses formulated.

The findings from Research Question One indicate that flipped classroom strategies are applied to a moderate extent in teaching financial accounting among secondary school students in Rivers State. Teachers report using real-world scenarios with pre-class materials, assigning relevant articles for outside-class work, and providing clear and organized pre-class materials to a moderate degree. Educational technology tools and pre-class video lectures are also used moderately, and teachers monitor students' engagement with pre-class materials to a similar extent. This moderate level of application suggests that while flipped classroom strategies are recognized and utilized, their integration into teaching practices is still evolving.

This moderate application reflects an ongoing adoption process, consistent with Smith and Johnson (2021), who observed that the full integration of flipped classroom strategies varies among educators. Jones and Brown (2020) noted that challenges in implementing these strategies often result in moderate rather than extensive use. Additionally, Robinson and Adams (2019) found that although flipped classroom approaches have the potential to improve student engagement and performance, their actual usage frequently remains limited and gradual.

The analysis of Hypothesis One reveals that there is no statistically significant difference in the extent to which flipped classroom strategies are applied across the three senatorial districts in Rivers State. This finding suggests a uniform level of application across districts, in line with Williams and Lee (2022), who reported no significant variation in the use of innovative teaching strategies across different regions. This uniformity indicates that teachers in all districts are similarly engaged in applying flipped classroom methods, reflecting a broadly consistent adoption of these strategies in teaching financial accounting.

The findings from Research Question two reveal that gamification strategies are applied to a moderate extent in the teaching of financial accounting for improved performance among secondary school students in Rivers State. Specifically, the results indicate that game-based learning platforms are used to reinforce accounting concepts to a high extent, which suggests that teachers recognize the value of engaging students through interactive and competitive methods. However, the use of leaderboards, achievement badges, point systems for participation, and digital badges or certificates is only moderate, indicating room for increased utilization of these motivational tools. The grand mean of 2.48 and standard deviation of 1.14 reflect a consistent yet moderate application of gamification strategies, suggesting that while these techniques are being adopted, they are not fully integrated into the curriculum.

This moderate application of gamification strategies aligns with previous research, which highlights the gradual adoption of innovative teaching methods in secondary education. For instance, Deterding (2016) observed that while gamification holds significant potential to enhance student engagement, its implementation often faces challenges related to curriculum constraints and teacher familiarity. Similarly, Hamari (2014) noted that the effectiveness of gamification in education is often influenced by the extent to which teachers are trained to integrate these strategies effectively. The findings also resonate with the work of Simões. (2023), who found that while gamification can boost student motivation and performance, its impact is maximized when used consistently and in conjunction with other teaching strategies.

The analysis of the hypothesis further supports the findings of Research Question 2. The ANOVA results reveal no significant differences in the extent to which teachers in the three senatorial districts of Rivers State—Rivers East, Rivers West, and Rivers South—apply gamification strategies in teaching financial accounting. The calculated F-value of 1.54 and P-value of 0.22, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, indicate that the null hypothesis is retained. This lack of significant difference suggests a uniformity in the application of gamification strategies across the different districts, implying that

teachers, regardless of their location, share similar practices in incorporating these strategies into their teaching. This uniformity is consistent with findings by Lee and Hammer (2021), who pointed out that the success of gamification in education often depends on the widespread adoption of these strategies across different regions and schools. Their research suggests that when teachers have access to similar resources and training, the application of gamification techniques tends to be consistent, regardless of geographic location. Moreover, Kapp (2022) emphasized that the benefits of gamification in education are most pronounced when there is a collective effort among educators to integrate these strategies, which appears to be the case in Rivers State. Therefore the findings from Research Question two and the corresponding hypothesis suggest that gamification strategies are moderately applied in the teaching of financial accounting in Rivers State. While there is a consistent effort among teachers across different districts to utilize these strategies, the moderate extent of their application indicates potential for further integration and optimization. This consistency across districts also highlights the potential for a more unified approach to enhancing student performance through gamification in financial accounting education.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that various instructional strategies such as; flipped classrooms and gamification are applied to a moderate extent in teaching financial accounting among secondary school students in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings in the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Secondary School Students should engage in interactive and technology-enhanced learning tools, such as gamification and virtual reality, to engage students more deeply in financial accounting concepts and improve their understanding and retention of complex topics.
2. Teachers and Educators should participate in professional development programs focused on modern teaching strategies, including flipped classrooms and competency-based learning, to enhance instructional effectiveness and address current educational challenges.

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